

A MULTIPLICITY PROBLEM RELATED TO SCHUR NUMBERS

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Abstract

For each natural number n , let C_n represent the set of all 2-colorings of the set $\{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. Given a natural number n and a coloring $\Delta \in C_n$, let $S(\Delta)$ represent the set

$$S(\Delta) = \{x_3 \mid \exists x_1, x_2 \text{ s.t. } x_1 + x_2 = x_3 \text{ and } \Delta(x_1) = \Delta(x_2) = \Delta(x_3)\}.$$

Given a natural number n , let

$$f(n) = \min_{\Delta \in C_n} S(\Delta).$$

For all natural numbers n and r where $\frac{n}{2} \leq r \leq n$, let $C_{n,r}$ represent the set of all 2-colorings of the set $\{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ where $\max\{|\Delta^{-1}(0)|, |\Delta^{-1}(1)|\} = r$. Given natural numbers n and r where $\frac{n}{2} \leq r \leq n$, let

$$f(n, r) = \min_{\Delta \in C_{n,r}} S(\Delta).$$

In this paper it is determined that for all natural numbers n ,

$$f(n) = \begin{cases} 0 & 1 \leq n \leq 4 \\ \lfloor \frac{n-3}{2} \rfloor & n \geq 5 \end{cases}$$

and for all natural numbers n and r where $n \geq 5$ and $\frac{n}{2} \leq r \leq n$,

$$f(n, r) = \begin{cases} r - 2 & r < n \\ r - 1 & r = n. \end{cases}$$

1. Introduction

Let \mathbb{N} represent the set of natural numbers and let $[a, b]$ denote the set $\{n \in \mathbb{N} \mid a \leq n \leq b\}$. A function $\Delta : [1, n] \rightarrow [0, t-1]$ is referred to as a t -coloring of the set $[1, n]$ or as a t -coloring

of length n . For every natural number n , let C_n represent the set of all 2-colorings of length n . For a given natural number n' where $n' < n$, a coloring Δ restricted to the set $[1, n']$ will be denoted by $\Delta|_{n'}$. Given a t -coloring Δ and a linear equation L in m variables, a solution (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m) to L is *monochromatic* if and only if $\Delta(x_1) = \Delta(x_2) = \dots = \Delta(x_m)$.

In 1916, I. Schur [21] proved that for every $t \geq 2$, there exists a least integer $n = Schur(t)$ such that for every t -coloring of length n , there exists a monochromatic solution to

$$x_1 + x_2 = x_3. \tag{1}$$

Note that the integers x_1 and x_2 need not be distinct. The integers $Schur(t)$ are called *Schur numbers*. It is known that $Schur(2) = 5$, $Schur(3) = 14$ and $Schur(4) = 45$, but no other Schur numbers are known [22]. A monochromatic solution to equation (1) is called a *monochromatic Schur triple*. In 1933, R. Rado found necessary and sufficient conditions to determine if an arbitrary system of linear equations admits a monochromatic solution for every coloring of the natural numbers with a finite number of colors [5, 15, 16, 17].

Recently, several other problems related to Schur numbers have been considered [1, 2, 3, 4, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14]. In 1996, R. Graham, V. Rödl and A. Rucinski proposed the following problem [6]. Find (asymptotically) the least number of monochromatic Schur triples that must occur in an arbitrary 2-coloring of length n . A problem of this nature where the number of monochromatic solutions is to be determined is referred to as a *multiplicity problem*. This problem was solved independently by A. Robertson and D. Zeilberger [19] and by T. Schoen [20] and was found to be $\frac{1}{22}n^2 + O(n)$.

In this paper we modify the problem of Graham, Rödl and Rucinski by asking the following question. In an arbitrary 2-coloring of length n , how many integers must there be that are the third integer (i.e. x_3) in at least one monochromatic Schur triple? For convenience in this paper, we shall refer to the third integer in any monochromatic Schur triple as *special*, formally defined below.

Definition 1. For every 2-coloring $\Delta : [1, n] \rightarrow [0, 1]$, an integer $s \in [1, n]$ is *special* if and only if there exist integers $x_1, x_2 \in [1, n]$, such that $x_1 + x_2 = s$ and $\Delta(x_1) = \Delta(x_2) = \Delta(s)$. The set of all special integers for a 2-coloring Δ is denoted by $S(\Delta)$.

Definition 2. For every natural number n , let

$$f(n) = \min_{\Delta \in C_n} S(\Delta).$$

In this paper it is determined that

$$f(n) = \begin{cases} 0 & 1 \leq n \leq 4 \\ \lfloor \frac{n-3}{2} \rfloor & n \geq 5. \end{cases}$$

More importantly, and perhaps more surprisingly, it is found that the number of special integers in a 2-coloring Δ is more directly related to the number of monochromatic integers

in Δ , rather than the length of Δ . For instance, the number of special integers that must occur in an arbitrary 2-coloring of length seventy with forty integers colored 0 is the same as the number that must occur in an arbitrary 2-coloring of length sixty with forty integers colored 0 or an arbitrary 2-coloring of length fifty with forty integers colored 0. We say that a coloring Δ has r monochromatic integers if $\max\{|\Delta^{-1}(0)|, |\Delta^{-1}(1)|\} = r$. For all natural numbers n and r where $\frac{n}{2} \leq r \leq n$, let $C_{n,r}$ represent the set of all 2-colorings of length n with r monochromatic integers.

Definition 3. For all integers n and r where $n \geq 5$ and $\frac{n}{2} \leq r \leq n$, let

$$f(n, r) = \min_{\Delta \in C_{n,r}} S(\Delta).$$

In this paper it is determined that

$$f(n, r) = \begin{cases} r - 2 & r < n \\ r - 1 & r = n. \end{cases}$$

The above formula for $f(n)$ follows immediately from this result.

2. Main Results

Theorem 1. If n and r are natural numbers such that $n \geq 5$ and $\frac{n}{2} \leq r \leq n$, then

$$f(n, r) = \begin{cases} r - 2 & \text{if } r < n \\ r - 1 & \text{if } r = n. \end{cases}$$

Proof. First we shall prove the case where $r = n$. Let a natural number $n \geq 5$ be given, let $r = n$ and let $\Delta : [1, n] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ be a coloring with r monochromatic integers. Clearly $S(\Delta) = [2, n]$, so $f(n, r) = r - 1$.

We shall now consider the case where $r < n$. First we shall show that $f(n, r) \leq r - 2$. Let integers n and r be given such that $n \geq 5$ and $\frac{n}{2} \leq r < n$. We shall exhibit a coloring $\Delta : [1, n] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ where $|\Delta^{-1}(0)| = r$ and $|S(\Delta)| = r - 2$. If $r = n - 1$ let Δ be defined by

$$\Delta(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & x = 1 \\ 0 & 2 \leq x \leq n. \end{cases}$$

It is clear that $S(\Delta) = [4, n]$ and that $|S(\Delta)| = n - 3 = r - 2$. If $r \leq n - 2$, let Δ be defined by

$$\Delta(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & 1 \leq x \leq n - r - 1 \\ 0 & n - r \leq x \leq n - 1 \\ 1 & x = n. \end{cases}$$

If $r = n - 2$, then $\Delta(S) = [4, n - 1]$; if $r = \frac{n}{2}$, then $\Delta(S) = [2, n - r - 1]$; and if $\frac{n}{2} < r < n - 2$, then $\Delta(S) = [2, n - r - 1] \cup [2n - 2r, n - 1]$. Since in each case $|S(\Delta)| = r - 2$, it follows that $f(n, r) \leq r - 2$.

Next we shall show that $f(n, r) \geq r - 2$ for all integers n and r where $n \geq 5$ and $\frac{n}{2} \leq r < n$. We will use induction on the integer n . When $n = 5$ we must consider the two cases of $r = 3$ and $r = 4$. Since the 2-color Schur number is 5, every 2-coloring of the set $[1, 5]$ with 3 monochromatic integers has at least 1 special integer, so $f(5, 3) \geq 1$. It is easy to check that every 2-coloring of the set $[1, 5]$ with 4 monochromatic integers has at least 2 special integers, so $f(5, 4) \geq 2$. In both cases $f(5, r) \geq r - 2$, so the basis step is complete. Now, let an integer $n_0 \geq 6$ be given. We may assume that

$$f(n, r) \geq r - 2 \text{ for every } n \in [5, n_0 - 1] \text{ and for every } r \text{ such that } \frac{n}{2} \leq r < n. \quad (2)$$

We must show that $f(n_0, r) \geq r - 2$ for all integers r such that $\frac{n_0}{2} \leq r < n_0$. Let an integer r such that $\frac{n_0}{2} \leq r < n_0$ be given and let a coloring $\Delta : [1, n_0] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ with r monochromatic integers be given. We must show that $|S(\Delta)| \geq r - 2$.

Without loss of generality, we may assume that Δ has r integers colored 0. If $\Delta(n_0) = 1$, then the coloring $\Delta|_{n_0-1}$ has r integers colored 0. If $r \leq n_0 - 2$, then by (2) it follows that $\Delta|_{n_0-1}$ has at least $r - 2$ special integers, so Δ does as well. If $r = n_0 - 1$ it has been previously shown that $\Delta|_{n_0-1}$ has $r - 1$ special integers. In each case $|S(\Delta)| \geq r - 2$, so we may assume that $\Delta(n_0) = 0$.

We shall consider three cases.

Case 1: Assume that $r > \frac{n_0+1}{2}$.

Since Δ has r integers colored 0 and $\Delta(n_0) = 0$, it follows that $\Delta|_{n_0-1}$ has $r - 1$ integers colored 0. Hence, from (2) we have that

$$|S(\Delta|_{n_0-1})| \geq r - 3,$$

so it suffices to show that n_0 is special. We shall consider the two subcases where n_0 is even and where n_0 is odd.

(i) Assume that n_0 is even. It follows that $r > \frac{n_0}{2}$.

If $\Delta(\frac{n_0}{2}) = 0$, then since $\Delta(n_0) = 0$ and $\frac{n_0}{2} + \frac{n_0}{2} = n_0$, it follows that n_0 is special. In this case we are done, so we may assume that $\Delta(\frac{n_0}{2}) = 1$.

Let $A = [1, \frac{n_0}{2} - 1] \cup [\frac{n_0}{2} + 1, n_0 - 1]$. Since there are $r - 1$ integers colored 0 in the set A and $r > \frac{n_0}{2}$, there are at least $\frac{n_0}{2}$ integers in the set A colored 0. For every $i \in [1, \frac{n_0}{2} - 1]$ let $A_i = \{i, n_0 - i\}$. Hence the set $\{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_{\frac{n_0}{2}-1}\}$ is a partition of the set A into $\frac{n_0}{2} - 1$ subsets and there exists an $i \in [1, \frac{n_0}{2} - 1]$ such that $\Delta(i) = \Delta(n_0 - i) = 0$. Then $(i, n_0 - 1, n_0)$ is a monochromatic Schur triple, so n_0 is special.

(ii) Assume that n_0 is odd.

This subcase is very similar to the n_0 even subcase. Let $A = [1, n_0 - 1]$ and for every $i \in [1, \frac{n_0-1}{2}]$, let $A_i = \{i, n_0 - i\}$. Since the set A has $r - 1$ integers colored 0 and $r - 1 \geq \frac{n_0-1}{2}$,

there exists an $i \in [1, \frac{n_0-1}{2}]$ such that $(i, n_0 - i, n_0)$ is a monochromatic Schur triple, so n_0 is special.

Since in both subcases n_0 is special and it was previously shown that $|S(\Delta|_{n_0-1})| \geq r - 3$, we have that $|S(\Delta)| \geq r - 2$.

Case 2: Assume that n_0 is even and $r = \frac{n_0}{2}$.

It follows that $\Delta|_{n_0-1}$ has $r - 1$ integers colored 0 and r integers colored 1. From (2) it follows that $\Delta|_{n_0-1}$ has at least $r - 2$ special integers, so Δ does as well and $|S(\Delta)| \geq r - 2$.

Case 3: Assume that n_0 is odd and $r = \frac{n_0+1}{2}$.

Since $n_0 - 2$ is odd, it follows that $\Delta|_{n_0-2}$ has $\frac{n_0-1}{2} = r - 1$ monochromatic integers. From (2) it follows that $\Delta|_{n_0-2}$ has at least $r - 3$ special integers, so it will be sufficient to show that $S(\Delta) \cap \{n_0 - 1, n_0\} \neq \emptyset$.

Recall that Δ has $r = \frac{n_0+1}{2}$ integers colored 0 and $\Delta(n_0) = 0$. Hence, exactly $\frac{n_0-1}{2}$ integers in the set $[1, n_0 - 1]$ are colored 0. Let $A = [1, n_0 - 1]$ and for every $i \in [1, \frac{n_0-1}{2}]$ let $A_i = \{i, n_0 - i\}$. Hence the set $\{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_{\frac{n_0-1}{2}}\}$ is a partition of the set A into $\frac{n_0-1}{2}$ subsets. If, for any $i \in [1, \frac{n_0-1}{2}]$, the set A_i is monochromatic in 0, then $(i, n_0 - i, n_0)$ is a monochromatic Schur triple and n_0 is special. In this case we are done, so we may assume that, for every $i \in [1, \frac{n_0-1}{2}]$, A_i contains one integer colored 0 and one integer colored 1.

Now we will prove the following claim.

Claim. *Let $\Delta(n_0 - 1) = a$ and let $b = 1 - a$. If $S(\Delta) \cap \{n_0 - 1, n_0\} = \emptyset$, then $\Delta(x) = b$ for every $x \in [1, \frac{n_0-1}{2}]$.*

Proof. Assume that the hypothesis of the claim is satisfied and note that $\{a, b\} = \{0, 1\}$. We shall show that $\Delta(\frac{n_0+1}{2} - i) = b$ for every $i \in [1, \frac{n_0-1}{2}]$ by using induction on i . First we shall show that

$$\Delta\left(\frac{n_0 + 1}{2} - 1\right) = b.$$

If $\Delta(\frac{n_0+1}{2} - 1) = a$, then $(\frac{n_0+1}{2} - 1, \frac{n_0+1}{2} - 1, n_0 - 1)$ is a monochromatic Schur triple and $n_0 - 1 \in S(\Delta)$, which is a contradiction. Hence, we may assume that $\Delta(\frac{n_0+1}{2} - 1) = b$.

Now, let $i_0 \in [2, \frac{n_0-1}{2}]$ be given and assume that $\Delta(\frac{n_0+1}{2} - (i_0 - 1)) = b$. We will show that

$$\Delta\left(\frac{n_0 + 1}{2} - i_0\right) = b.$$

Now, $A_{\frac{n_0+3}{2}-i_0} = \{\frac{n_0+1}{2} - (i_0 - 1), \frac{n_0-3}{2} + i_0\}$. Since $A_{\frac{n_0+3}{2}-i_0}$ contains an integer colored a , it follows that

$$\Delta\left(\frac{n_0 - 3}{2} + i_0\right) = a.$$

If $\Delta\left(\frac{n_0+1}{2} - i_0\right) = a$, then $\left(\frac{n_0-3}{2} + i_0, \frac{n_0+1}{2} - i_0, n_0 - 1\right)$ is a monochromatic Schur triple and $n_0 - 1 \in S_3(\Delta)$, which is a contradiction. Hence, we may assume that $\Delta\left(\frac{n_0+1}{2} - i_0\right) = b$ and the proof of the claim is complete. \square

Now, as noted above, if $S(\Delta) \cap \{n_0 - 1, n_0\} \neq \emptyset$, then $|S(\Delta)| \geq r - 2$. If $S(\Delta) \cap \{n_0 - 1, n_0\} = \emptyset$, then from the claim we have that $\Delta(x) = b$ for every $x \in [1, \frac{n_0-1}{2}]$. This implies that $[2, \frac{n_0-1}{2}] \subseteq S(\Delta)$ and that $|S(\Delta)| \geq \frac{n_0-3}{2} = r - 2$. In either case we have that $|S(\Delta)| \geq r - 2$, so we are done with Case 3.

Since in all three cases we showed that $|S(\Delta)| \geq r - 2$, the proof of Theorem 1 is complete. \square

We are now ready to state and prove Theorem 2. The theorem follows directly from previous results.

Theorem 2. *For every natural number n ,*

$$f(n) = \begin{cases} 0 & 1 \leq n \leq 4 \\ \lfloor \frac{n-3}{2} \rfloor & n \geq 5. \end{cases}$$

Proof. The case where $1 \leq n \leq 4$ follows directly from the fact that the 2-color Schur number is 5. If $n \geq 5$, then every coloring of the set $[1, n]$ contains at least $\lfloor \frac{n+1}{2} \rfloor$ monochromatic integers. From Theorem 1 it follows that every coloring of the set $[1, n]$ contains at least $\lfloor \frac{n+1}{2} \rfloor - 2 = \lfloor \frac{n-3}{2} \rfloor$ special integers. \square

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